

Algebraic Structure and Classification of Idempotents in Multicomplex Spaces \mathbb{C}_n

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ABSTRACT:

In this paper, we introduce the multicomplex space \mathbb{C}_n generated by n commuting imaginary units and develop its fundamental algebraic framework. We define the algebraic operations on \mathbb{C}_n and establish that it possesses a natural structure of a modified Banach algebra. A systematic study of idempotent elements in \mathbb{C}_n is carried out, including their explicit construction, classification into trivial, basic, primitive, and compound types, and their organization according to levels. Furthermore, we investigate the norm structure of idempotent elements and determine all possible norm values, providing explicit formulas and low-dimensional illustrations. The results unify the algebraic and metric aspects of multicomplex algebras and offer a clear structural understanding of idempotents in \mathbb{C}_n , which may be useful for further developments in multicomplex analysis and functional algebra.

Keywords and phrases. Multicomplex Space; Idempotent element; Trivial and Non-trivial idempotent elements; primitive idempotents; compound idempotents; Modified Banach algebra.

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1. Introduction

Multicomplex numbers generalize the classical complex system by introducing several commuting imaginary units. The resulting algebra \mathbb{C}_n includes bicomplex and tricomplex numbers as special cases and provides a unified setting for various hypercomplex structures useful in analysis and mathematical physics. Idempotent elements play a central role in the structural study of \mathbb{C}_n because they generate canonical decompositions and simplify algebraic and analytic operations. While idempotents in low-dimensional multicomplex spaces are well studied, a systematic classification for general \mathbb{C}_n , together with their norm behavior, has not been fully developed. This paper establishes the algebraic framework of \mathbb{C}_n , shows that it forms a modified Banach algebra under a suitable norm, and provides a concise classification of all idempotent elements into trivial, basic, primitive, and compound types. We also determine the possible norms of idempotents and present explicit formulas supported by low-dimensional examples.

2. Multicomplex Space \mathbb{C}_n

In this section, we introduce the concept of the multicomplex space and describe its fundamental algebraic and metric structures.

Let

$$\mathbb{C}_n = \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n-1}, i_n)$$

denote the **multicomplex space** generated by the commuting imaginary units

$$i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n.$$

The multicomplex algebra \mathbb{C}_n is defined recursively by

$$\mathbb{C}_n = \{ \zeta + i_n \eta : \zeta, \eta \in \mathbb{C}_{n-1} \}.$$

The imaginary units satisfy the relations

$$i_1^2 = i_2^2 = \dots = i_{n-1}^2 = i_n^2 = -1, \\ i_p i_q = i_q i_p, \quad 1 \leq p, q \leq n, p \neq q.$$

Let

$$\mathcal{V}_1 = \zeta_1 + i_n \eta_1, \quad \mathcal{V}_2 = \zeta_2 + i_n \eta_2 \in \mathbb{C}_n,$$

where $\zeta_1, \eta_1, \zeta_2, \eta_2 \in \mathbb{C}_{n-1}$.

2.1 Algebraic Operations on \mathbb{C}_n

(i) Addition:

$$+ : \mathbb{C}_n \times \mathbb{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_n$$

$$\mathcal{V}_1 + \mathcal{V}_2 = (\zeta_1 + i_n \eta_1) + (\zeta_2 + i_n \eta_2) = (\zeta_1 + \zeta_2) + i_n(\eta_1 + \eta_2).$$

(ii) Multiplication:

$$\times : \mathbb{C}_n \times \mathbb{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_n$$

$$\mathcal{V}_1 \times \mathcal{V}_2 = (\zeta_1 + i_n \eta_1) \times (\zeta_2 + i_n \eta_2) = (\zeta_1 \zeta_2 - \eta_1 \eta_2) + i_n(\zeta_1 \eta_2 + \zeta_2 \eta_1)$$

(iii) Scalar multiplication:

$$\cdot : F \times \mathbb{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_n$$

$$\alpha \cdot \mathcal{V} = \alpha(\zeta + i_n \eta) = \alpha \zeta + i_n(\alpha \eta), \quad \alpha \in F$$

(iv) Norms in Multicomplex Spaces \mathbb{C}_n :

We first introduce the norms on $\mathbb{C}_0, \mathbb{C}_1, \mathbb{C}_2$ and \mathbb{C}_3 since they play a fundamental role in multicomplex analysis by establishing the basic geometric and metric structures from which higher-order norms on \mathbb{C}_n are naturally constructed.

(N1) Norm in \mathbb{C}_0

Let \mathbb{C}_0 be the field of real numbers.

For any real number $x \in \mathbb{C}_0$, the norm is defined by

$$\|x\|_0 = |x| = \begin{cases} x, & x \geq 0, \\ -x, & x < 0. \end{cases}$$

This norm measures the usual distance of x from the origin on the real number line.

(N2) Norm in \mathbb{C}_1

Let \mathbb{C}_1 denote the field of complex numbers.

For any complex number $z = x + iy \in \mathbb{C}_1$, the norm is defined by

$$\|z\|_1 = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} = \sqrt{z\bar{z}},$$

Where $\bar{z} = x - iy$ denotes the complex conjugate of z .

(N3) Norm in \mathbb{C}_2

(i) $\xi = x_1 + i_1 x_2 + i_2 x_3 + i_1 i_2 x_4$

$$\|\xi\|_2 = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2},$$

(ii) $\xi = z_1 + i_2 z_2$

$$\|\xi\|_2 = \sqrt{\|z_1\|_1^2 + \|z_2\|_1^2},$$

(iii) Norm of Idempotent form

$\xi = (z_1 - i_1 z_2) e_{1,2} + (z_1 + i_1 z_2) e_{-1,2}$

$$\|\xi\|_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\|z_1 - i_1 z_2\|_1^2 + \|z_1 + i_1 z_2\|_1^2}{2}}$$

(N4) Norm in \mathbb{C}_3 :

(i) $\zeta = x_1 + i_1 x_2 + i_2 x_3 + i_3 x_4 + i_1 i_2 x_5 + i_1 i_3 x_6 + i_2 i_3 x_7 + i_1 i_2 i_3 x_8, \quad x_i \in \mathbb{C}_0$

$$\|\zeta\|_3 = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 + x_5^2 + x_6^2 + x_7^2 + x_8^2}$$

(ii) $\zeta = z_1 + i_2 z_2 + i_3 z_3 + i_2 i_3 z_4, \quad z_1, z_2, z_3, z_4 \in \mathbb{C}(i_1)$

$$\|\zeta\|_3 = \sqrt{\|z_1\|_1^2 + \|z_2\|_1^2 + \|z_3\|_1^2 + \|z_4\|_1^2}$$

(iii) $\zeta = \xi + i_3 \eta, \quad \xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2)$

$$\|\zeta\|_3 = \sqrt{\|\xi\|_2^2 + \|\eta\|_2^2}$$

(iv) Norm in idempotent form

Let $\zeta = \xi + i_3\eta$, $\xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2)$

Then,

$$\zeta = (\xi - i_1\eta)e_{1,3} + (\xi + i_1\eta)e_{-1,3} = (\xi - i_2\eta)e_{2,3} + (\xi + i_2\eta)e_{-2,3}.$$

$$\|\zeta\|_3 = \sqrt{\frac{\|\xi - i_1\eta\|_2^2 + \|\xi + i_1\eta\|_2^2}{2}} = \sqrt{\frac{\|\xi - i_2\eta\|_2^2 + \|\xi + i_2\eta\|_2^2}{2}}.$$

(v) Norm in Canonical Idempotent Basis :

$$\zeta = \alpha e_4 + \beta e_5 + \gamma e_6 + \delta e_7, \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1)$$

$$e_4 = e_{1,2} e_{1,3}, \quad e_5 = e_{1,2} e_{-1,3}, \quad e_6 = e_{-1,2} e_{1,3}, \quad e_7 = e_{-1,2} e_{-1,3},$$

$$\|\zeta\|_3 = \sqrt{\frac{\|\alpha\|_1^2 + \|\beta\|_1^2 + \|\gamma\|_1^2 + \|\delta\|_1^2}{4}}$$

(N5) Norm in the Multicomplex Space \mathbb{C}_n

(i) Let $\mathcal{V} = \zeta + i_n\eta$, $\zeta, \eta \in \mathbb{C}_{n-1}$

Define the norm

$$\|\cdot\|: \mathbb{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_0$$

by

$$\|\mathcal{V}\|_n = \sqrt{\|\zeta\|_{n-1}^2 + \|\eta\|_{n-1}^2}$$

(ii) Let $\mathcal{V} = x_1 + i_1x_2 + \dots + (i_1i_2 \dots i_n)x_{2^n}$

$$\|\mathcal{V}\|_n = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{2^n} x_i^2}$$

3. Algebraic Structure of \mathbb{C}_n

Since we are interested in equipping \mathbb{C}_n with a meaningful algebraic structure, we first examine its fundamental algebraic properties.

Let \mathbb{C}_n be the set of multicomplex numbers. Define the binary operation of addition

$$+ : \mathbb{C}_n \times \mathbb{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_n$$

in the usual componentwise manner. With this operation, $(\mathbb{C}_n, +)$ forms an Abelian group.

Let F denote the field of scalars, which we take to be $\mathbb{C}_0 = \mathbb{R}$. Define scalar multiplication by

$$\cdot : F \times \mathbb{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_n.$$

With addition and real scalar multiplication, the triple $(\mathbb{C}_n, +, \cdot)$ becomes a real linear space.

Moreover, for every canonical representation of elements of \mathbb{C}_n , there exists a natural embedding of \mathbb{C}_n into an appropriate finite-dimensional linear space.

In particular, \mathbb{C}_n can be embedded into the Euclidean space $\mathbb{C}_0^{2^n}$, to which it is algebraically isomorphic.

Let

$$\|\cdot\|: \mathbb{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_0$$

be the norm defined previously. Since the space $\mathbb{C}_0^{2^n}$ is complete with respect to the Euclidean norm, it follows that \mathbb{C}_n , endowed with this norm, is complete. Consequently, the quadruple $(\mathbb{C}_n, +, \cdot, \|\cdot\|)$ is a **Banach space**.

Next, equip \mathbb{C}_n with the multiplication $\times: \mathbb{C}_n \times \mathbb{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_n$ defined earlier. With respect to this multiplication, \mathbb{C}_n becomes an algebra with unit element, usually denoted by 1.

However, it is important to note that $(\mathbb{C}_n, +, \times, \cdot, \|\cdot\|)$ is **not** a Banach algebra in the classical sense, since the standard submultiplicative inequality

$$\|\mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{V}\|_n \leq \|\mathcal{U}\|_n \|\mathcal{V}\|_n, \quad \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{V} \in \mathbb{C}_n,$$

does not hold in general.

Instead, \mathbb{C}_n satisfies the estimate

$$\|\mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{V}\|_n \leq 2^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \|\mathcal{U}\|_n \|\mathcal{V}\|_n$$

which is known to be the best possible inequality in this setting.

Therefore, \mathbb{C}_n constitutes a **modified Banach algebra**.

Finally, for every $n \geq 1$, the space \mathbb{C}_n is algebraically isomorphic and isometrically isomorphic to each of the spaces

$$\mathbb{C}_0^{2^n}, \quad \mathbb{C}_1^{2^{n-1}}, \dots, \mathbb{C}_{n-2}^4, \quad \mathbb{C}_{n-1}^2.$$

Hence, the family $\mathbb{C}_n, n \geq 1$ forms a natural class of finite-dimensional modified Banach algebras.

4. Classification of idempotents in multicomplex algebras \mathbb{C}_n

1. Conventions and definitions

(i) **Algebras.** Let \mathbb{C}_n denote the multicomplex algebra generated by commuting imaginary units i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n . We use the recursive embedding

$$\mathbb{C}_{k-1} \subset \mathbb{C}_k.$$

(ii) **Idempotent.** An element $e \in \mathbb{C}_n$ is idempotent if $e^2 = e$.

(iii) **Trivial idempotents (fixed convention).**

In this paper, we adopt the convention that the only trivial idempotents in any multicomplex algebra \mathbb{C}_n are the elements $\{0,1\}$. Every other idempotent is regarded as non-trivial. The idempotents 0 and 1 first appear in the base algebra $\mathbb{C}_0 = \mathbb{R}$, the field of real numbers, and therefore they are referred to as trivial idempotents throughout this work.

(iv) Explicit Structural Form of Basic Idempotents

All basic idempotents in a multicomplex algebra arise from pairs of imaginary units and are of the standard form:

$$e_{rs} = \frac{1 + i_r i_s}{2}, \quad e_{-rs} = \frac{1 - i_r i_s}{2}, \quad 1 \leq r < s \leq n.$$

(v) Level of an Idempotent Element

The level of an idempotent e is the smallest index r such that

$$e \in \mathbb{C}_r \text{ but } e \notin \mathbb{C}_{r-1}.$$

We write $\text{Level}(e) = r$.

(vi) Primitive Idempotent

An idempotent e in a commutative algebra is **primitive** if:

1. $e^2 = e$
2. $e \neq 0, 1$
3. It cannot be written as a non-trivial sum of two orthogonal idempotents.

That is,

$$e = f + g, \quad fg = 0 \implies f = 0 \text{ or } g = 0.$$

So a primitive idempotent captures an **indecomposable component** of the algebra's decomposition.

(vii) Compound idempotent

Any idempotent that is neither trivial nor primitive is called **compound**. Such elements can be expressed as products, complements, or sums of orthogonal primitive idempotents.

4.1 Classification by Levels

(i) \mathbb{C}_0 (Real Numbers)

- Idempotents: $\{0,1\}$ (level – 0).

(ii) \mathbb{C}_1 (complex numbers)

- Idempotents: $\{0,1\}$. (no new idempotents arise in \mathbb{C}_1).

(iii) \mathbb{C}_2 (Bicomplex)

- Total idempotents

$$|\text{Idem}(\mathbb{C}_2)| = 2^{2^1} = 4.$$

- Explicit set :

$$\left\{ 0, 1, e_{12} = \frac{1 + i_1 i_2}{2}, e_{-12} = \frac{1 - i_1 i_2}{2} \right\}.$$

Classification in \mathbb{C}_2 :

- **Trivial** : $\{0, 1\}$ (these belong to $\mathbb{C}_0 \subset \mathbb{C}_2$).
- **Non-trivial Basic Primitive** (appear first in \mathbb{C}_2 , level-2):

$$e_{12}, e_{-12}.$$

• **Idempotent decomposition of \mathbb{C}_2 :**

The algebra

$$\mathbb{C}_2 = \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2)$$

admits a canonical decomposition in terms of its two primitive idempotents

$$e_{12}, e_{-12}$$

For each $k = 1, 2$

$$\mathbb{C}_2 = \mathbb{C}(i_k) e_{12} + \mathbb{C}(i_k) e_{-12}.$$

The primitive idempotents e_{12}, e_{-12} ensure the uniqueness of this decomposition, and they satisfy

$$(e_{12})^2 = e_{12}, \quad (e_{-12})^2 = e_{-12}, \quad e_{12}e_{-12} = 0, \quad e_{12} + e_{-12} = 1.$$

(iv) \mathbb{C}_3 (Tricomplex)

Total idempotents

$$|\text{Idem}(\mathbb{C}_3)| = 2^{2^2} = 16.$$

Classification in \mathbb{C}_3 :

(a) **Trivial** : { 0, 1}

(b) **Total Basic idempotent that appear at or before \mathbb{C}_3** : 6

- Level-2 Basic idempotent (from \mathbb{C}_2): 2

$$e_{12}, e_{-12}.$$

- Level-3 Basic idempotent (first appear in \mathbb{C}_3): 4

$$e_{13}, \quad e_{-13}, \quad e_{23}, \quad e_{-23}.$$

(c) Primitive idempotents of \mathbb{C}_3

Total primitive idempotents

$$|\text{Prim}(\mathbb{C}_3)| = 2^{3-1} = 4.$$

Explicitly:

$$c_1 = e_{12}e_{13} = \frac{1}{4} (1 + i_1i_2 + i_1i_3 - i_2i_3), \quad c_2 = e_{12}e_{-13} = \frac{1}{4} (1 + i_1i_2 - i_1i_3 + i_2i_3),$$

$$c_3 = e_{-12}e_{13} = \frac{1}{4} (1 - i_1i_2 + i_1i_3 + i_2i_3), \quad c_4 = e_{-12}e_{-13} = \frac{1}{4} (1 - i_1i_2 - i_1i_3 - i_2i_3).$$

Idempotent decomposition of \mathbb{C}_3 :

$\mathbb{C}_3 = \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$ admits a canonical decomposition in terms of its four primitive idempotents

$$c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4$$

For each $k = 1, 2, 3$ the algebra \mathbb{C}_3 decomposes into four copies of the complex field generated by i_k .

Explicitly,

$$\mathbb{C}_3 = \mathbb{C}(i_k)c_1 + \mathbb{C}(i_k)c_2 + \mathbb{C}(i_k)c_3 + \mathbb{C}(i_k)c_4.$$

The primitive idempotents c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4 ensure the uniqueness of this decomposition, and they satisfy the standard relations

$$c_j^2 = c_j, \quad c_jc_k = 0 \quad (j \neq k), \quad c_1 + c_2 + c_3 + c_4 = 1.$$

(d) Compound idempotents:

$$|\text{Comp}(\mathbb{C}_3)| = 2^{2^{3-1}} - 2^{3-1} - 2 = 10$$

Full table of idempotents in C_3

SN	Idempotent	Explicit Value	Level	Type	Decomposition / Remark
1	0	0	0	Trivial	Zero element
2	1	1	0	Trivial	Unity element
3	e_{12}	$\frac{1+i_1i_2}{2}$	2	Compound (basic pair)	$e_{12} = c_1 + c_2$
4	e_{-12}	$\frac{1-i_1i_2}{2}$	2	Compound (basic pair)	$e_{-12} = c_3 + c_4$
5	e_{13}	$\frac{1+i_1i_3}{2}$	3	Compound (basic pair)	$e_{13} = c_1 + c_3$
6	e_{-13}	$\frac{1-i_1i_3}{2}$	3	Compound (basic pair)	$e_{-13} = c_2 + c_4$
7	e_{23}	$\frac{1+i_2i_3}{2}$	3	Compound (basic pair)	$e_{23} = c_2 + c_3$
8	e_{-23}	$\frac{1-i_2i_3}{2}$	3	Compound (basic pair)	$e_{-23} = c_1 + c_4$
9	$e_{12}e_{13}$	$\frac{1}{4}(1+i_1i_2+i_1i_3-i_2i_3)$	3	Primitive	c_1
10	$1 - e_{12}e_{13}$	$\frac{1}{4}(3-i_1i_2-i_1i_3+i_2i_3)$	3	Compound	$c_2 + c_3 + c_4$
11	$e_{12}e_{-13}$	$\frac{1}{4}(1+i_1i_2-i_1i_3+i_2i_3)$	3	Primitive	c_2
12	$1 - e_{12}e_{-13}$	$\frac{1}{4}(3-i_1i_2+i_1i_3-i_2i_3)$	3	Compound	$c_1 + c_3 + c_4$
13	$e_{-12}e_{13}$	$\frac{1}{4}(1-i_1i_2+i_1i_3+i_2i_3)$	3	Primitive	c_3
14	$1 - e_{-12}e_{13}$	$\frac{1}{4}(3+i_1i_2-i_1i_3-i_2i_3)$	3	Compound	$c_1 + c_2 + c_4$
15	$e_{-12}e_{-13}$	$\frac{1}{4}(1-i_1i_2-i_1i_3-i_2i_3)$	3	Primitive	c_4
16	$1 - e_{-12}e_{-13}$	$\frac{1}{4}(3+i_1i_2+i_1i_3+i_2i_3)$	3	Compound	$c_1 + c_2 + c_3$

(v) \mathbb{C}_4

Total idempotents

$$|\text{Idem}(\mathbb{C}_4)| = 2^{2^3} = 256.$$

Classification in \mathbb{C}_4 :

(a) **Trivial:** $\{0, 1\}$

(b) **Total Basic idempotent that appear at or before \mathbb{C}_4 :** 12

- Level-2 Basic idempotent : 2
- Level-3 Basic idempotent : 4
- Level-4 Basic Idempotents : 6

Explicitly:

$$e_{\pm 1,4} = \frac{1 \pm i_1 i_4}{2}, \quad e_{\pm 2,4} = \frac{1 \pm i_2 i_4}{2}, \quad e_{\pm 3,4} = \frac{1 \pm i_3 i_4}{2}.$$

(c) **Primitive idempotents of \mathbb{C}_4**

Total primitive idempotents

$$|\text{Prim}(\mathbb{C}_4)| = 2^{4-1} = 8.$$

Idempotent decomposition of \mathbb{C}_4 :

The multicomplex algebra $\mathbb{C}_4 = \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4)$ admits a canonical decomposition in terms of its eight primitive idempotents.

For each $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$ the algebra \mathbb{C}_4 decomposes into eight copies of the complex field generated by i_k .

$$\mathbb{C}_4 \cong (\mathbb{C}(i_k))^8.$$

(d) **Compound idempotents:**

$$|\text{Comp}(\mathbb{C}_4)| = 2^{2^{4-1}} - 2^{4-1} - 2 = 246$$

(vi) **The General Multicomplex Algebra \mathbb{C}_m (for $m \geq 1$)**

Total number of idempotents

$$|\text{Idem}(\mathbb{C}_m)| = 2^{2^{m-1}}.$$

Classification in \mathbb{C}_m :

(a) **Trivial:** $\{0, 1\}$

(b) **Total Basic idempotent that appear at or before \mathbb{C}_m :** $m(m - 1)$

New basic idempotents introduced at level- m : $= 2(m - 1)$

Explicitly:

$$e_{\pm r,m} = \frac{1 \pm i_r i_m}{2}, \quad r = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1.$$

(c) **Primitive idempotents of \mathbb{C}_m**

Total primitive idempotents

$$|\text{Prim}(\mathbb{C}_m)| = 2^{m-1}.$$

Idempotent decomposition of \mathbb{C}_m :

The multicomplex algebra $\mathbb{C}_m = \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m)$ admits a canonical decomposition in terms of its 2^{m-1} primitive idempotents.

For each $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$ the algebra \mathbb{C}_m decomposes into 2^{m-1} copies of the complex field generated by i_k .

$$\mathbb{C}_m \cong (\mathbb{C}(i_k))^t, \quad t = 2^{m-1}.$$

(d) **Compound idempotents:**

$$|\text{Comp}(\mathbb{C}_m)| = 2^{2^{m-1}} - 2^{m-1} - 2.$$

5. Norms of Idempotent Elements in Multicomplex Algebras \mathbb{C}_n

We consider the standard multicomplex norm induced by the Euclidean structure on the real representation of \mathbb{C}_n .

5.1 Norm Values of Idempotents

Let $e \in \mathbb{C}_n$ be an idempotent, i.e., $e^2 = e$. Then the norm of e is of the form

$$\|e\|_n = \sqrt{\frac{k}{2^{n-1}}}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^{n-1}.$$

Consequently, the spectrum of possible norm values is

$$\left\{ \sqrt{\frac{k}{2^{n-1}}}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^{n-1} \right\},$$

and the number of distinct norms equals

$$2^{n-1} + 1.$$

5.2 Low-Dimensional Cases

To illustrate the pattern, we list the data for small n :

n	$ \text{Idem}(\mathbb{C}_n) $	Possible Norms	# Distinct norms
1	2	$\left\{ \sqrt{\frac{0}{1}}, \sqrt{\frac{1}{1}} \right\}$	2
2	4	$\left\{ \sqrt{\frac{0}{2}}, \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}, \sqrt{\frac{2}{2}} \right\}$	3
3	16	$\left\{ \sqrt{\frac{k}{4}} : k = 0, 1, \dots, 4 \right\}$	5
4	256	$\left\{ \sqrt{\frac{k}{8}} : k = 0, 1, \dots, 8 \right\}$	9

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we established the algebraic structure of the multicomplex spaces \mathbb{C}_n and showed that, under an appropriate norm, they form a modified Banach algebra. We provided a complete level-wise classification of idempotent elements—trivial, basic, primitive, and compound—and described their role in the canonical decomposition of \mathbb{C}_n . The norm analysis demonstrated that idempotents in \mathbb{C}_n exhibit a structured and predictable pattern across levels. These results unify the properties of bicomplex and tricomplex systems and extend them to the general multicomplex framework, offering a foundation for further work in spectral theory, functional calculus, and applications in analysis and mathematical physics.

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